

Psychological, Physical, and Physiological Risks of Pursuing the Ideal Body Type

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Abstract: Body image is a complex concept that includes many factors such as generation, culture, subculture, country of origin, personal experience, and social expectation. In this day and age of instant gratification and accessibility of information technology, the issues that stem from body image are vast and deep, often leading to dangerous mental and physical health risks, like depression, anxiety, dysmorphia, and eating disorders. The common ideals that are accepted in society today have evolved from what was considered trendy in different eras, like how in the United States, they have phased from having healthy bodies to flat stomachs. In adolescence, teenagers experience a lot of natural physical change while also being exposed to content in social media, making it difficult to not experience body dissatisfaction. Athletes also experience poor body image because in their environment, they are always surrounded by pressure from their peers and mentors. There are many types of beauty standards in different countries and cultures, but they all lead to unhealthy and unnatural strategies in order to meet these standards. For example, China, South Korea, Russia, and Western culture have all established the similar standard that having a slimmer body type is what makes someone beautiful. Manipulating one's negative mindset to be positive will be difficult, but some things to keep in mind while befriending one's body is to try and avoid discouraging content on social media and unhealthy ways to lose weight, discuss struggles with friends or professionals, and learn how other people challenged and overcame their body dissatisfaction. The purpose of this paper is to explore all the consequences and risks of pursuing what we refer to as an "ideal body type" in an effort to reduce unhealthy standards and make our way to a more balanced and equitable future.

Keywords: body image, mental health, mental illness, body shaming, beauty standards.

I. INTRODUCTION

Personally, the idea of body image has always been an interesting topic, as everyone has different views and attitudes about it. Even if negative opinions of our body are somewhat normalized, it is important to know at what point professional help is needed. It is a common, universal idea that having a slim body is the ideal body type, but how did this come to be in the first place? Society today, especially with Covid-19 and quarantine, has heavily relied on social media to escape from the real world and live vicariously through others. Some of the content that can be viewed on social media include pictures of models and pretty influencers, which especially as a teenager, may lead to a lowered self-esteem. Comparing my body has become a natural way of thinking, which is a very negative mindset that I know can be changed with the right resources. If I am experiencing poor body image as a Korean, adolescent female, how is body image viewed in other cultures and parts of the world, or at different ages? I believe learning about body image and its potential risks on mental health and overall wellness can help improve our perspectives. It is time that the toxic environments created online and in person are changed, so that people become more aware and understanding about how people can be different. It is also important to learn and study the risks so that we can resolve pre-existing threats, or recognize and avoid those risks for the future. For some, even if it is difficult to accept that appearance is not essential in daily life, I believe that at the end of the day, our health needs to be prioritized instead. Knowing about the possible dangers can lead our minds into the reality of the effects of negative body image on all aspects of our lives.

II. MENTAL ILLNESS

A. *Depression and Anxiety*

Attempting to achieve the ideal body type comes with many risks, including those relating to mental health. Depression is a mental illness where one experiences deep sadness and loss of interest, and this can occur when one is, "...upset with one's specific aspect of one's life, [which] leads to being upset with one's life more generally"¹. The lack of food intake from the fear of weight gain could also trigger depressive behavior like decreases in energy and enthusiasm, bringing about exhaustion and negative feelings. A type of anxiety tied to body image is Social Physique Anxiety (SAP), where one feels they would be judged based on their figure. The environment is a significant contributing factor, since peers and important adults like parents, teachers, and coaches could all pressure someone to have an 'appropriate' appearance and weight, forcing the person to cover up and become insecure. The decrease in confidence would then make someone less likely to go out and socialize, forming an introverted mindset.

B. *Dysmorphia*

Body dysmorphic disorder is the distorted outlook on one's body. Body Dysmorphic Disorder (BDD) can be caused by the environment of the person, like abuse or bullying, lack of confidence, fear of isolation, perfectionism, or competition. If, "...[one finds oneself] spending a lot of time obsessing over, hiding, or trying to correct what [they] see as flaws"², they would most likely have BDD, as this is more severe than having normal insecurities. When common insecurities become serious, that is when it becomes a health risk; some signs and symptoms of BDD are picking of the skin, intensely avoiding getting pictures taken, getting plastic surgery to correct multiple flaws, seeking repeated reassurance, or suicidal thoughts from dissatisfaction. People with BDD are also vulnerable to social anxiety, because of their growing paranoia of judgment from others.

C. *Self-Injury*

People experiencing body dissatisfaction have gone through extreme lengths to reach their goal of their interpretation of the 'perfect body'. Self-injury can be associated with control, as people who want control over themselves would gain it through unhealthy ways. Girls are more susceptible to self injury because of this, while boys with superiority complexes would use this lack of control to harm others. Some examples of self-injury can include eating disorders, severe dieting and exercise, and self harm. The struggles of eating disorders are difficult to manage, as it could potentially lead to substance abuse, like the misuse of laxatives or diet pills, and further permanent health consequences, like broken down muscle or brain damage. Common eating disorders tied to negative body image are anorexia nervosa and bulimia nervosa. An anorexic person would obsessively watch their weight and fear weight gain, while a bulimic person would binge eat, then purge. Psychologically, anorexia could cause perfectionism and behavioral inflexibility, where, "...there [is] one 'right way' to do things"³. Substance abuse usually comes with bulimia, as the addiction of purging becomes endless, and since, "Bingeing and purging temporarily removes stress, like a drug"⁴. Especially during adolescence, eating disorders have been difficult to discover because of indistinct factors, like how, "...a teenage girl or young woman who is anorexic can fall under the medical radar because her weight is normal or even overweight"⁵. It is dangerous as more and more children are being exposed to social media and the socially accepted body figure, developing insecurities at a young age, and putting them at a greater risk of eating disorders and hazardous behaviors. Lack of confidence and self-esteem, two very common feelings, are huge contributors to actions relating to self-injury, putting many people at risk. Attempting to achieve perfection comes with the physical risks of permanent damage to the body and never ending cycles of pain.

III. PHILOSOPHY OF IDEAL BODY TYPE, STANDARD OF BEAUTY

Every era in the timeline is defined by the standard of beauty, or the ideal look accepted by society, as it shapes what people looked like back in the day.

1980-2000: Throughout the 1980s, curvy, athletic bodies were trending. Aerobic exercise and fitness shows encouraged women to become fit, starting obsessions with fitness and becoming thin. However, in the 1990s, or the 'Heroin Chic' era, the focus was brought back to being thin, but also featuring, "Waifish...translucent skin...[and looking] androgynous"⁶. The too thin and neutral look was all the rage, creating a huge difference from the fit and healthy body type in the 90s. Eating disorders, like anorexia, and obesity peaked during this time, creating a, "...divide in the way bodies are presented across the media"⁷.

2000-2010: In the 2000s, levels of low self confidence increased due to the popularization of social media platforms. The standard body type beginning this era was having a flat stomach, large breasts and butt, a thigh gap, and maintaining a healthy but thin figure. An example of this would be, “Kim Kardashian...[who] is the poster woman of ideal...standards for the modern woman”⁶. The ability for people to control what they post online created toxic environments for insecure people, since it was easy to target and cyber bully behind the screen.

2010-Present: Beginning its rise in the 2010s, social media became more understanding of the diverse body types that exist in society. More representation was shown in advertisements, like how, “In 2015, Robyn Lawley was the first plus-size model featured...”⁷. This is important because advertising different body types can change the perspectives of people blinded by the ‘ideal’ beauty standard. But even with this, people still get discouraged from watching and scrolling through pictures of models and celebrities, showing how the decades before this pushed the idea that skinny is beautiful for so long that it became a universal standard of beauty.

IV. TYPES OF BODY IMAGE

Body image is a mental representation of how one views their appearance. There are four different types of body image, which are perceptual, affective, cognitive, and behavioral. Perceptual body image is the way that someone sees themselves as, which is not always correct. An example of having a perceived view of body types is when a person might think that they are, “...fat when in reality they are underweight”⁸, which establishes an unhealthy mindset. It could also be described as the failure to accurately depict one’s physique. Affective body image is how one feels about their body and appearance, like their likes and dislikes of themselves. These feelings are important because they can influence someone’s opinions of themselves into a different, more negative perspective. Cognitive body image is what someone thinks and believes about their body. Beliefs include the idea that one can only be happy with themselves if they become thin. Something that could help settle body negativity is Cognitive-behavioral therapy or CBT, which is, “...a form of talk therapy...[that] can help [one] identify harmful, faulty thinking patterns...so they’re kinder and more accurate”⁹. Lastly, behavioral body image is the things someone does in response to their dissatisfied body. This is when physical actions are taken to achieve a goal resulting in weight loss, which are influenced by perceptual, affective, and cognitive body image issues. Some behaviors include excessive exercise, obsessive dieting, unhealthy eating habits, and disordered eating. Self-acceptance is an important trait to develop in order to battle negative body image, because then, people would be able to recognize false information spread by the environment and people around them.

V. BODY SHAMING

Body shaming someone means to criticize one’s appearance, body shape, or size. It has become normalized in many different ways, and often hard to recognize because of its many disguises. Even if it is not said out loud, people tend to turn to criticism, which comes from negative feelings, like being upset or annoyed, or in forms of defense or intimidation. This includes thoughts like, ‘His outfit was so ugly today’, or, ‘At least we don’t look like her’, or even thoughts directed towards oneself, like, ‘I look like an elephant standing next to her’. Because of the established idea in society where being thin can bring upon happiness, many people are unable to be satisfied with their bodies. These are high expectations to meet, since everyone has their own body type, so people should, “...aim to be healthy and confident in who they are...and it’s time society accepted [them] as such”¹⁰. Body shaming can also be seen in our daily lives in more subtle manners, like dress codes at school. School dress code policies often target women significantly, lowering their confidence and increasing their insecurities when called out by adults for what they wear. The dress code enacted at a young age could also amplify the false idea that women have to dress accordingly if they have respect for themselves, instead of the idea that men have to understand that, “...just because a girl’s body is showing does not mean she’s open for sex”¹¹. The content promoted in the media also contributes to the constant body shaming of others, because it creates an environment where it makes it easier for people to compare themselves to others and judge. Many advertisements and sponsors display thin, pretty models, as well as in video games and cartoons, where it is very rare to see overweight characters who were not created to mock big bodies. Overall, even though body shaming has been subtly implemented into people’s lives, the media and the mindsets of people have been changing for the better, and more representation can be seen.

VI. BODY IMAGE IN ADOLESCENTS

Adolescence is a critical time for development and changes in the body. They go through, “Pubertal changes, including increased body fat...”¹², which is considered negative changes to the body, increasing body dissatisfaction. Also during puberty, because of the hormonal changes, quick mood changes occur, making them more vulnerable to thinking negatively

of themselves. This vulnerability can connect to depression and anxiety because the mood disturbance, "...induces selective attention to negative information about oneself and the world"¹². Depressive moods could also be caused by dieting, where adolescents turn to eating less as they become serious about becoming skinnier.

Teenagers become more aware of cultural and ethnic pressures displayed through the different beauty standards, creating more external pressure to become 'beautiful'. As for familial pressure, many members make comments on how one's body has evolved, such as, "You've gotten skinnier since the last time I saw you!", or, "Have you been going to the gym?", rewarding the teens for changing. Pressure from outside sources become more influential during the adolescent period, solidifying the mindset that they have to transform their bodies. This begins the journey through obsessive exercise and eating disorders, developing dangerous problems and habits that are difficult to get rid of. Although maintaining a healthy body should be an obvious lifestyle to follow, it is often forgotten about as a teen's main focus is the result, which is thinness or muscularity. Movies and television shows directed towards teenagers promote thinness and beauty, often teasing the overweight or scrawny characters. Other contributors are Barbie dolls or action figures, advertising unrealistic body types. Because teenagers use and absorb social media more, they are more exposed to images of the accepted appearance. External and internal pressures are very effective during adolescence, an important growing period in life, making them susceptible to unhealthy risks.

VII. BEAUTY STANDARDS IN CHINA

Beauty culture in China is very extreme, because of its high standard established at young ages from family members, and peer, cultural, and societal pressure. This ideal beauty standard for women calls for fair skin, a skinny body, tiny waist, long legs, and large eyes with double eyelids, while men have to have fair skin, a muscular but slim build, and tall height. A lot of influence for these beauty standards emerge from popular trends and fitness challenges on social media, such as one challenge where women, "...prove their waists did not protrude behind a vertical...piece of paper"¹³. These challenges contribute towards increasing the intensity of pressure towards the audience, as it becomes more tempting to participate in the popular trends. The misconception of body image created by these trends leads to a demand for surgery, like breast augmentation, liposuction, and eyelid surgery. Although plastic surgery can be used for confidence boosts and satisfaction, it is very dangerous and, "unnecessary for teenagers...because their bodies are still changing during puberty"¹⁴. Western culture has also influenced the view of body image in China, boosting the demand for operations relating to height. There are many common Chinese sayings regarding physical characteristics, such as "Slim down, flaws gone", and "White skin covers many flaws"¹⁵. As popular sayings are introduced in the household, like how a woman's role in the family is to maintain their appearance and physique, they would be established and repeated as a standard at an early age. In a Chinese legacy, there is a one-child policy, enforcing more pressure for children to be perfect. Also, traditionally it is thought by parents that being skinny is connected to popularity as well as success, creating a never-ending pursuit of beauty. This type of familial, cultural, and societal pressure exposed to younger audiences makes them more vulnerable to develop dangerous habits such as anorexia, extreme dieting, and the usage of laxative and thinning medication, and depression, social anxiety, and body dissatisfaction.

VIII. BEAUTY STANDARDS IN SOUTH KOREA

In Korea, the high beauty standard and strictness in the environment make it difficult for women to avoid body dissatisfaction and plastic surgery. K-pop idols and Korean actors are performers who only fit the unrealistic beauty standard. If a woman does not have a slim body, symmetrical face, large eyes, "...a round shaped forehead, double eyelids, puffy...eyebags, a modest...sized nose bridge, 'V-line face' and extremely pale...skin"¹⁶, then they cannot be accepted into society as 'pretty'. Culturally, dark skin is connected to poverty and working under the sun, so having white skin is very emphasized, normalizing the skin bleaching procedure. This dangerous practice includes the use of whitening pills, creams, and soaps, which can be very harmful and toxic. Relating to skin, Korean cosmetics and skincare products became a global phenomenon. The increase in consumers publicized the products more, advertising more models with unbelievably clear skin, enhancing one's self consciousness and insecurities. Having acne and rough skin is not ideal to have in the culture, so many turned to dermatologists and popularized skincare lines. As for body type, K-pop idols and actors are known for their tiny waists and slim legs, causing women with healthy builds to feel overweight. Low self-esteem can lead to depression and a severe weight problem developing from young ages. Also in Korea, being pretty is an important trait to have in life, as, "Those who...are not pretty have tremendous difficulty to achieve social and professional success"¹⁶. For example, employers require a headshot with one's resume to judge their skill by looks. The want for change that comes with this

competition starts the obsession for transforming appearance. With this, the pressure to change one's appearance comes from themselves, instead of from external resources. Ultimately, the Korean media is a major contributor in establishing high and unrealistic beauty standards, increasing the want for change and putting the consumers of famous products and procedures at risk.

IX. BEAUTY STANDARDS IN RUSSIA

In Russian culture, there is a widespread conservatism regarding race, gay rights, and most of all, the female body. Even though the Russian population is very diverse, there is a common high beauty standard held in this society, which is being tall, thin, blonde, and blue-eyed. It is important for the women to look put together, elegant, and feminine no matter where they are going, even when running errands. Everything they wear is with purpose, as, "They are in the habit of being beautiful, of actively choosing and caring about their appearance"¹⁷. Most of the time, this purpose is to appeal to men, which is an on-going concept brought upon by the conservatism. Maintaining one's image is also inspired by the high standard of beauty in other parts of their culture, like the beautifully built churches. In the Russian media, the general perception of eating disorders is that it does not become dangerous until medical intervention is necessary. Messages are also spread, mainly through a popular social media platform called VKontakte, "...about several topics and even [glorifying] eating disorders and [sharing] tips on the kind of pills that [helps one] stay 'perfect'"¹⁸. Unrealistic body types have become the normal standard spread throughout the media, causing its audience to believe that it is healthy to be super thin. Pressure from the health care system, school, and family is also present in the form of fat-phobia and body shaming. Females are encouraged to follow the idea that 'beauty is pain', and that it is normal to, "...suffer uncomfortable high heels and restrictive diets as long as it delivers a socially-admirable appearance"¹⁹. Familial pressure could also include buying clothes to purposely cover up body fat. Despite the traditional conservative ideologies and high standards, Russian feminism has been on the rise, challenging these concepts and spreading body positivity throughout the media.

X. BEAUTY STANDARDS IN WESTERN CULTURE

The culture evolved from Western countries, like the United States and Europe, has influenced many parts of the world with its high standards regarding body image. While non-Western countries value plump body types, thinness and unhealthy weights are celebrated in Western countries, as, "...they often engage in unhealthy weight control practices, including dietary restrictions...to conform to the social norms of beauty"²⁰. The advertising and representation in the media distorts people's minds into having a desire to lose weight and change their bodies to be happy. From movies promoting muscularity, like Rambo, to television programs encouraging slimming down, like Extreme Weight Loss, it has become difficult for people to avoid these subtle messages in their everyday lives. Not only does this affect people living in the west, but, "...a significant number of Western television programmes have been adapted to different countries and dubbed..."²¹, showing the spread and domination of the culture. Western actors and actresses are stereotypically beautiful and skinny, also inspiring their audience to idolize and be like them. Especially for children and adolescents, they receive pressure from not only social media, but from school and parents. Little things, like being weighed as a part of a physical fitness test during school, or being praised for looking skinnier, can go a long way, as far as developing mental and physical health problems. It is also very dangerous for the younger generation because they are around their parents, who have been living through western culture, all the time, making their, "...desire to lose weight [to be] strongly influenced by their parents' attitudes, behaviors and direct comments regarding [the parents'] or their children's weight"²⁰. They could also be wrongly taught at a young age about what weight is acceptable to have in society, which could affect their opinions later in life about which body weight is healthy.

XI. INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA

Even though the themes displayed on social media now are able to promote body positivity and help for eating disorders, it has not always been like that. The media can be a dangerous place, and it can make the user more susceptible to cyber bullying, peer pressure, social anxiety, and low body confidence. Seeing other people's posts initiates self-consciousness and awareness, beginning a risky journey into body image. Being able to post oneself onto the internet for others to see can lead one to, "...seek validation through comments and likes, comparing the way [they] look to the people [they] see on social media..."²².

A. 1980-2000

During the 80s, supermodels and athletic bodies were emphasized, popularizing magazines like Playboy, and aerobic exercise shows. Encouraging its audience to become fit, this would turn the standard of beauty into one that is healthy. But in the 90s, the focus turned to a body type with a tiny waist and big breasts, put into perspective by the movie 'Baywatch'. Straying away from the healthy and fit body type, "...thinness alone and a bony appearance"²³ was more accepted. Many models on runways and advertisements were below the healthy average weight which was difficult to achieve, leaving the audience desperate to achieve this body type.

B. 2000-2020

Beginning in the 2000s, new applications for social media such as Facebook, Youtube, Twitter, Tumblr, Pinterest, and Instagram, started to become normalized. A new platform for posting your own content comes with a new sense of freedom, where one can control what one sees and shares. But with this, also comes unrealistic expectations for our physical traits and potentially help develop negative body image. Triggering a need for change, filters and applications similar to photoshop are used to 'fix' appearances and become the person that you want to be. Fitness trends, like SoulCycle, promoted exercise and strength, and advertising to get fit may be motivational, but it could also make people feel self-conscious of their body.

C. 2020-present

In 2020, the social media platform 'TikTok', became a massive sensation. This is a place where people can post fifteen to sixty second videos, sharing any type of content from comedy to dancing videos. The people who get famous through TikTok are called 'TikTok Stars', and many of them are pretty with thin, defined body types. Even though the creators are posting videos that cover many topics, the fact that they all share the same trendy standard of beauty are indirectly lowering the confidence of their audiences. But, as TikTok developed, more and more advocates of body positivity and creators with advice about body image joined and enlightened their audience.

XII. BODY IMAGE IN ATHLETES

Athletes and active people have different experiences with body image as they put themselves in a new environment. Surrounded by people with a variety of fitness goals, it makes it hard for others with slow-paced plans to not feel pressured to match the high level energy of others. In a gym setting, people are there to maintain or work on their shape, but it can be a, "...threat to body image, inducing self-objectification (e.g., social comparisons...evaluations by others, and the presence of mirrors)"²⁴. People in the gym are vulnerable to comparing their bodies with others, because they are surrounded by fit and active people. For some, their pride may be damaged seeing others with healthier, more muscular, or thinner bodies, adding to one's insecurities. But, when people become regulars in the gym, seeing skinnier people around them could be a motivator, and help one recognize that personal progress matters more than physical change. Athletes in particular are also exposed to this environment, "...developing body image disorders because of the pressures surrounding sport performance and...trends promoting muscularity and leanness"²⁵. Because athletes are competitors, it is even more challenging to avoid comparing oneself to another, creating a space where they have to get used to being around people that are stronger, faster, or more skilled. However, competition could lead to an unhealthy obsession with being the best, leading to more problems such as anxiety, eating disorders, and unhealthy dieting. As active people adapt to their surroundings, they are able to cope with their body image because, "...they experience situations that require coping more frequently"²⁴. Even though people who try to better themselves by working on their health have courage to get up and be active, at the same time, they situate themselves into the dangers of being self-conscious, and overcoming external pressure to acceptance.

XIII. SOLUTIONS

Although there are many resources that contribute to body shaming and negative body image, as the media grows, so does the content that combats these. To start, the audience is able to control what they see on their feed, creating the opportunity to eliminate and unfollow any discouraging posts. Another beneficial strategy can be avoiding discriminatory advertisements promoted by celebrities and models, like weight-loss tea or fitness trackers. Furthermore, interacting with uplifting and educational posts about body positivity can create a healthier, more satisfying algorithm. Growing from low self-confidence also means, "...unlearning what [has] been taught from media sources"⁹, and challenging those messages. Learning more about strong mindsets is also able to create a new appreciation for the reality that there is a widespread diversity of body types in society. Other solutions include professional help, like Cognitive Behavioral Therapy, which can,

“...help [one] identify harmful, faulty thinking patterns and restructure [one’s] thoughts...”⁹. Low self-esteem and negative body image is a common contributor for social anxiety and depression, so discussing this topic with others can offer a different perspective towards attitude. Another healthy way to combat these mental obstacles is to practice, “Healthy amounts of physical activity [, which can] release endorphins (feel-good chemicals)”⁹. Taking care of the body is also an important factor, since body dysmorphia and low self confidence can potentially develop eating disorders. Eating healthful foods may be important, but developing the freedom of eating whatever someone wants without regret is more impactful. Self-care, compassion, and acceptance are important traits to have in the process of loving oneself again, which can be learned through others who have experienced the same negative thoughts.

XIV. PERSONAL REFLECTION

As a Korean female, even though I have had less pressure on my appearance because I have not been living in Korea, I was still exposed to Korean culture through social media, like the K-pop industry. The music in Korea is also known for the experience of watching the music videos, so even at a young age, I was allowed to watch those videos and see the pretty idols and their body types. Aside from cultural pressure, I have always felt pressure through my friends and the people around me, being unable to evade my thoughts from comparing myself to them. The popular western beauty standard, that being skinny was the ideal body type, has always been what I considered acceptable, making it difficult for me to decide what is considered skinny, and what is not. When I was growing up, it was normal to hear comments about somebody’s body, normalizing a form of bullying during a stage of development. Fat and body shaming jokes were also normalized, and for some, these jokes would be taken seriously, even if the jokes were not said to cause any harm. Although through social media, I learned about the variety of different body types and how beautiful they are, somehow I am still unable to be satisfied with my own body. Now that I am at the adolescent stage, it has been especially difficult to accept the way that I look because of all the necessary physical changes that my body has to go through. Going on social media and surfing the web has become something that has been added to my daily routine, making it easier for me to compare myself to the content that I see. I also am an athlete, which inevitably puts me in an environment where people have toned, slim bodies. I cannot help but think that I am not working hard enough when I come back from practice to see no change in my body, and I would not have an accurate view from the extra bloat from drinking water. In my head, I know that I am not considered fat in society, but when lounging on my bed or in my chair, I cannot help but notice the extra fat overlap on my stomach. Changing my opinion of myself has been a challenging experience, but after reading other people’s stories and their struggles, it has helped me accept my body more. While researching about the different beauty standards around the world and potential risks that come with this obsession of body image, I realized that as long as I am healthy, I am lucky to be in this body.

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